

Fractures in Large Animals and Their Management

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Fractures are commonly observed in large animals such as cattle, buffaloes, and horses. These injuries typically occur in long bones of the forelimbs and hindlimbs, as well as in the pelvis and mandible. Young animals are particularly vulnerable, especially in cases of dystocia, where rough handling is involved. Although the overall prevalence of fractures in large animals is relatively low (approximately 0.95%), they remain a significant clinical concern due to their impact on animal welfare and productivity.

Fractures in large animals often result from external trauma, self-inflicted injuries, slipping or falling, mishandling during machinery use, kicking by herd mates. These injuries frequently lead to lameness, which in turn negatively affects milk yield and quality. Key clinical signs include reluctance or inability to bear weight, resistance to walking, and visible limb deformities.

Studies have shown that cattle are more commonly affected than buffaloes, with females being more susceptible overall. Cattle tend to suffer more from hindlimb fractures, particularly involving the metatarsals and tibia, while buffaloes are more prone to forelimb fractures, especially of the metacarpals (Yadav et al., 2019).

Fractures are typically classified into two types. Closed fractures where the skin remains intact. Open fractures where the bone is exposed through the skin. Open fractures are more commonly reported in cattle due to their thinner, more fragile skin and higher tendency to agitate the injury site.

Immediate first aid is critical to prevent infection, especially in open fractures, where the risk of bone infection and poor healing outcomes is significantly higher. Unfortunately, many farmers

house animals on kutcha (unpaved) floors, increasing exposure to dirt and reducing the chances of successful healing.

In closed fractures, where the bone remains enclosed within the skin, prognosis is better and healing tends to be quicker due to faster callus formation.

Basic On-Farm Stabilization

It can be performed using readily available materials clean water, cotton or clean cotton cloth, bamboo sticks (length matching the limb), nada rolls or cotton bandages. Stabilization can be done by casting the animal with the fractured limb positioned upward, Keep the limb straight using gentle traction. In open fractures, clean the wound thoroughly with clean water. If bone is exposed, attempt gentle repositioning using sterile instruments (e.g., scissors), if feasible. Apply diluted povidone-iodine (Betadine) solution to disinfect the wound. After drying, cover the limb with ample cotton padding. Place bamboo splints on all four sides (front, back, on sides). Secure splints with cotton strips or nada rolls — firm enough to stabilize, but not so tight as to impair blood circulation.

These are temporary measures. The animal must be taken to the nearest veterinary hospital for professional treatment.

Clinical Management and Advanced Support

Veterinarians may use aluminum splints or fiberglass casts to provide better support. Antibiotics, anti-inflammatories, and other supportive medications are prescribed as needed. If pus formation is observed, the cast must be replaced, and the wound reassessed.

Typically, fiberglass casts are removed after about 45 days, but if healing is incomplete, they may be retained for an additional 15 days. Radiography plays a crucial role in monitoring healing and guiding further management.

This fibreglass management may provide adequate support to the fractured part, but sometimes that is not enough. Different kind of fractures like green stick, transverse, oblique, spiral etc. needs different way of support. Like in some of the fractures, pinning is most appropriate while in others plating is used as primary support while in others some ancillary support with screws or wires. Intramedullary pinning is done to prevent bending forces. Cross pinning prevents torsion and bending forces. Transfixation prevents torsion, compression along with bending forces on the other hand plating cannot prevent bending forces but resist rest all. So, surgeon experience matters most to choose what kind of technique should actually be used. Still after all these efforts to repair a fracture, if the surgery is delayed or there is osteomyelitis, there may be failure of fracture to heal. There can be non-union, mal-union at the fracture site. Bone densities are better visible in radiographs, so only modality to check if there is complete callus formation is radiography. Again, all these surgical treatments are not that successful in large animals. This might be due to more weight of animals, pins and plating are not able to support completely, along with this, animals are kept on farms, which do not provide adequate clean environment to keep the surgical wound free from infection.

Special Considerations in Horses

Fractures in horses, especially open fractures, pose additional challenges. Their skin is more delicate and prone to infection and proud flesh formation (excessive granulation tissue), which delays healing significantly. Therefore, fracture care in equines requires particular vigilance and hygiene.

Conclusion

Large farm animals are prone to fractures but often do not outwardly show signs of pain. Prompt diagnosis, appropriate first aid, and veterinary intervention are essential to ensure effective recovery. Preventive measures, including careful handling and proper flooring, can go a long way in reducing the incidence of fractures and improving the overall well-being of livestock.

References

- Yadav, G. P., Sangwan, V., & Kumar, A. (2019). Comparative occurrence pattern of fractures in cattle and buffaloes. *Veterinary World*, 12(7), 1154–1159. <https://doi.org/10.14202/vetworld.2019.1154-1159>